

INTERSECTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND END BAD GOVERNMENT MOVEMENT AMONG PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MANGU LGA, PLATEAU STATE: IMPLICATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT.

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Intersection of Social Media, End Bad Government Movement, Public Senior Secondary School Students, Educational Management.

Abstract: *This study investigated the intersection of social media and the "End Bad Government" movement among public senior secondary school students in Mangu Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State and its implications for educational management. A descriptive survey research design was used for this study. The population of the study consisted of 3,100 registered teachers with the sample of 310 respondents (teachers) that is 10% from 10 secondary schools. A self-structured questionnaire titled "Intersection of Social Media and End Bad Government Movement among Public Senior Secondary School Students: Implications for Educational Management" (ISMEBGPSSSIMGQ) was used as the instrument for data collection. The instrument was validated by two experts, one from the department of Educational administration and planning and the other from the Department of Psychology and Guidance and Counseling, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while the null hypothesis was tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The bench mark for decision making was 2.50. The study concludes by recommending enhanced dialogue between administrators and students, inclusive policy development and more..*

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INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's "End Bad Government" movement is a potent sociopolitical movement propelled by a general dissatisfaction with systemic inefficiencies, corruption, and governance shortcomings (Agbaje, 2021). The emergence of this movement, which is primarily led by young people, is a reaction to the ongoing problems with Nigerian governance, including as unemployment, poverty, and insecurity, as well as the lack of accountability and transparency among political leaders (Ajayi, 2020). The EndSARS protests in October 2020, which at first focused on calling for reforms to the government but soon grew to include more demands than only ending police brutality, gave the campaign a major boost (Oluwole, 2021). The "End Bad Government" movement has been greatly organized and amplified by social media (Ekong, 2020). Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Twitter have become essential tools for political engagement because of their capacity to support real-time communication, protest mobilization, and information dissemination to a global audience (Ihejirika & Ugorji, 2022). Particularly students have utilized social media in previously unimaginable ways to plan protests, voice grievances, and hold officials responsible (Nwachukwu, 2020). Furthermore, social media has democratized the dissemination of information, providing voice to marginalized people and inspiring protestors throughout the globe to unite (Adekoya, 2021).

In a networked setting, social media refers to the online platforms and tools that let people create, share, and interact with content. These platforms, which have proven essential to communication, organization, and mobilization—especially in the context of political movements—include social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and messaging apps like WhatsApp (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Social media has completely changed political movements all around the world by offering a decentralized platform for planning demonstrations, disseminating information, and upending established power structures. The Arab Spring (2010-2011) is often cited as a key example of social media's role in political movements. During these protests, social media platforms like Twitter and Facebook were used to organize mass demonstrations and disseminate real-time information, helping to topple long-standing authoritarian regimes in Tunisia, Egypt, and Libya (Howard & Hussain, 2013). The success of these movements demonstrated the power of social media to mobilize people and facilitate political change in a way that was not possible before.

Social media has been instrumental in a number of political movements in Nigeria. Due in large part to its popularity on social media sites like Twitter, the Bring Back Our Girls movement from 2014—which aimed to bring attention to the kidnapping of more than 200 schoolgirls by Boko Haram—attracted attention from around the world (Kassahun, 2014). The EndSARS movement, which emerged in 2020,

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demonstrated the effectiveness of social media in coordinating demonstrations against police brutality. Social media was the main vehicle for coordination, information sharing, and gaining support from around the world during the movement's rapid transformation from an online campaign to large-scale rallies throughout Nigeria (Olonisakin, Ojebode, & Falola, 2021). These instances demonstrate how social media has become into a vital instrument for political activism, especially in situations when traditional media is restricted.

The influence of social media on student behavior and academic performance is a subject of considerable debate. On one hand, social media can have positive effects by facilitating access to information, enabling collaboration, and fostering social connections among students (Junco, 2012). For instance, educational platforms like YouTube and academic groups on Facebook can provide students with additional learning resources, allowing them to enhance their understanding of various subjects outside the classroom. However, there are also significant negative effects associated with excessive use of social media. Research has indicated that extended usage of social media might cause diversions, shorten students' attention spans, and have a detrimental effect on their academic achievement (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). According to Karpinski et al. (2013), students may put their use of social media above their academic obligations, which can cause them to procrastinate and do worse academically. Furthermore, kids may experience stress, anxiety, and other behavioral problems as

a result of being exposed to cyber bullying, peer pressure, and offensive information on social media platforms, which may further impair their academic performance (Hawi & Samaha, 2016). Educational management refers to the administration and organization of educational institutions, which includes maintaining discipline, ensuring a conducive learning environment, and responding to external influences such as political activism (Bush, 2007). Student activism, particularly in the digital age, presents unique challenges for educational managers. With the rise of social media, students are increasingly engaging in political activism, often using their educational institutions as platforms for mobilization and protest. Educational managers must navigate the delicate balance between supporting students' rights to free expression and maintaining order within the institution. Failure to address student activism effectively can lead to disruptions in the academic environment, strained relationships between students and administration, and potential long-term impacts on the institution's reputation and functioning (Altbach, 1989). As such, educational managers need to develop strategies that allow for constructive dialogue and engagement with student activists while ensuring that academic activities are not adversely affected. Several case studies highlight the different approaches educational institutions have taken in response to student activism:

University of Cape Town, South Africa (2015-2016): During the Fees Must Fall movement, which sought to address the high cost of university education and systemic

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inequalities, the University of Cape Town experienced significant student protests. The university administration initially responded with a heavy-handed approach, including the use of private security and police to quell protests. However, this approach was met with backlash and further intensified the protests. Eventually, the university shifted towards dialogue and negotiations with student leaders, which helped to de-escalate tensions and address some of the students' demands (Naicker, 2016).

University of California, Berkeley, USA

(2017): In response to a series of politically charged protests on campus, including those related to free speech and the presence of controversial speakers, UC Berkeley's administration adopted a strategy that emphasized the importance of maintaining a safe and inclusive environment while upholding the principles of free speech. The university implemented policies that regulated the time, place, and manner of protests, ensuring that while students' rights to protest were protected, academic activities could continue without significant disruption (Cohen, 2018).

Lagos State University, Nigeria (2020):

During the EndSARS protests, Lagos State University faced significant student participation in the movement. The university administration initially attempted to discourage student involvement by threatening disciplinary actions. However, this approach was counterproductive and led to increased student unrest. The administration eventually adopted a more conciliatory approach by engaging with student representatives and allowing peaceful protests

on campus, which helped to maintain order while respecting students' rights to political expression (Nwabueze, 2020). These case studies demonstrate the importance of flexibility, dialogue, and respect for students' rights in managing political activism within educational institutions. Effective educational management in the context of student activism requires a balanced approach that addresses students' concerns while maintaining the integrity and stability of the academic environment.

In Plateau State, and specifically within Mangu Local Government Area (LGA), the "End Bad Government" movement has resonated strongly among public senior secondary school students (Mohammed, 2022). Mangu, a region that has experienced its share of socio-political challenges, including communal conflicts and economic hardships, has seen its youth increasingly turn to social media to express their discontent with the status quo (Danjuma, 2021). The movement has provided these students with a platform to engage in political discourse, challenge authority, and demand better governance, reflecting the broader national trend of youth-led activism (Yusuf, 2021).

Despite the efforts of the government and other stakeholders to curtail the movement, it continues to thrive (Adediran, 2021). The Nigerian government has employed various strategies to suppress the protests, including the use of force, the imposition of curfews, and attempts to regulate social media platforms (Onuoha, 2020). Additionally, educational institutions and local authorities in Mangu have

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attempted to manage the situation by discouraging student participation in protests, implementing strict policies on social media use, and promoting dialogue between students and administrators (Bala & Ibrahim, 2022). Religious and community leaders have also stepped in, advocating for peace and urging the youth to seek non-violent means of addressing their grievances (Tanko, 2020). However, despite these efforts, the movement persists, driven by the deep-seated dissatisfaction with governance and the sense of empowerment that social media provides (Afolayan, 2021). The continued engagement of students in the "End Bad Government" movement presents significant challenges for educational management in Mangu LGA. If these issues are not adequately addressed, they could lead to disruptions in the academic environment, increased tensions between students and school authorities, and potential long-term impacts on the educational system (Omolayo, 2022). Educational managers must navigate the delicate balance between maintaining order and discipline within schools while acknowledging and addressing the legitimate concerns of students who are increasingly politically aware and active (Umar, 2021).

Failure to attend to the effects of this movement on educational management could result in a breakdown of the educational process, further alienation of students from school authorities, and the erosion of the trust and respect necessary for a conducive learning environment (Ibrahim, 2021). Therefore, it is imperative to explore the intersection of social media and the "End Bad

Government" movement among students in Mangu LGA, with a focus on developing effective strategies for educational management in the face of ongoing political activism (Okoro, 2022).

Objectives of the Study

The study examines Intersection of Social Media and End Bad Government Movement among Public Senior Secondary School Students in Mangu LGA, Plateau State: Implications for Educational Management. Specifically, the study aims:

1. To explore the influence of social media on male and female students' involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement.
2. To assess the implications of this involvement for educational management in Mangu LGA.
3. To propose strategies for managing the impact of social media-driven activism in secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions will serve as a guide to this work.

1. What role do social media play in the involvement of male and female public Senior Secondary School Students in the "End Bad Government" movement?
2. How does this involvement affect the management of educational institutions?
3. What strategies can be employed by educational managers to address the challenges posed by social media-fueled activism?

Research hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant difference between male and female public senior secondary school students in the role that social media plays in

their involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement.

Methodology

In this study, a descriptive survey research design was adopted. 3,100 registered teachers working in secondary schools in Plateau State's Mangu Local Government Area made up the target population. 10% of the total population, or 310 teachers, were chosen at random to make up the study sample. These instructors were drawn from ten different secondary schools. The "Intersection of Social Media and End Bad Government Movement among Public Senior Secondary School Students: Implications for Educational Management" (ISMEBGPSSSIMGQ) self-structured questionnaire was used to gather data. The survey used a four-point Likert scale: Agree (A)

= 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Strongly Agree (SA) = 4. The instrument was validated by two experts: one from Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State's Department of Educational Administration and Planning, and the other from the Department of counseling, guidance, and psychology. The research issues were addressed using mean and standard deviation, and the null hypothesis was examined at 0.05 significance level using t-test statistics. An interpretive cutoff point of 2.50 was established for the outcomes.

Results and Discussions

Research Question One: What role do social media play in the involvement of male and female public Secondary School Students in the "End Bad Government" movement?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the role social media play in the involvement of male and female public Secondary School Students in the "End Bad Government" movement.

S/ N	Item Statements	Mea n	SD	Remar k
1.	Social media platforms are equally influential in encouraging both male and female students to participate in the "End Bad Government" movement.	2.65	.63	Agree
2.	Male students are more likely than female students to engage in the "End Bad Government" movement through social media.	2.72	.65	Agree
3.	Female students are more cautious in expressing their views on the "End Bad Government" movement through social media compared to male students.	2.53	.59	Agree

4.	Social media has made it easier for both male and female students to organize protests related to the "End Bad Government" movement.	2.59	.61	Agree
5.	The content shared on social media about the "End Bad Government" movement resonates equally with both male and female students.	2.68	.64	Agree
Average Mean		2.63	0.62	Agree

N=310

Data in Table 1 revealed that item 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 had mean scores above the mean bench mark of 2.50, this implies that respondents agreed that social media platforms are equally influential in encouraging both male and female students to participate in the "End Bad Government" movement, that male students are more likely than female students to engage in the "End Bad Government" movement through social media, that female students are more cautious in expressing their views on the "End Bad Government" movement through social media compared to male students, that social media has made it easier for both male and female students

to organize protests related to the "End Bad Government" movement, and that the content shared on social media about the "End Bad Government" movement resonates equally with both male and female students. However, from the responses of the respondents one can find that social media plays a significant role in the involvement of male and female public Secondary School Students in the "End Bad Government" movement as indicated by the average mean score of 2.63.

Research Question Two: How does this involvement affect the management of educational institutions?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on how this involvement affect the management of educational institutions.

S/ N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
6	Student involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement disrupts the normal functioning of educational institutions.	2.71	.65	Agree
7	The movement has increased tension between students and educational administrators.	2.72	.65	Agree
8	Schools are struggling to manage student activism related to the "End Bad Government" movement.	2.87	.69	Agree

9	Involvement in the movement has led to a decline in academic performance among students.	2.67	.63	Agree
10	The "End Bad Government" movement has necessitated changes in school policies and management strategies.	2.65	.63	Agree
Average Mean		2.72	0.6	Agree
			5	

N=310

Data in Table 2 revealed that item 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 had mean scores above the mean bench mark of 2.50, this implies that respondents agreed that student involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement disrupts the normal functioning of educational institutions, that the movement has increased tension between students and educational administrators, that schools are struggling to manage student activism related to the "End Bad Government" movement, that involvement in the movement has led to a decline in academic performance among students, and that the "End Bad

Government" movement has necessitated changes in school policies and management strategies. However, from the responses of the respondents one can find that students involvement in "End Bad Government" movement has significant effects on the management of educational institutions to a high extent as indicated by the average mean score of 2.72.

Research Question Three: What strategies can be employed by educational managers to address the challenges posed by social media-fueled activism?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on strategies that can be employed by educational managers to address the challenges posed by social media-fueled activism.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
11	Educational managers should engage directly with students to address their concerns related to the "End Bad Government" movement.	2.81	.68	Agree
12	Implementing clear guidelines on acceptable student behavior related to social media use would reduce the challenges posed by activism.	2.68	.64	Agree
13	Educational institutions should provide training for staff on how to manage social media-fueled student activism.	2.78	.67	Agree

14	Promoting open communication between students and educational managers can help in mitigating the effects of social media activism.	2.68	.64	Agree
15	Schools should collaborate with parents to monitor and guide students' social media use in relation to activism.	2.52	.59	Agree
Average Mean		2.69	0.6	Agree
			4	

N=310

Data in Table 3 revealed that item 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 had mean scores above the mean benchmark of 2.50, it implies that respondents agreed that educational managers should engage directly with students to address their concerns related to the "End Bad Government" movement, that implementing clear guidelines on acceptable student behavior related to social media use would reduce the challenges posed by activism, that educational institutions should provide training for staff on how to manage social media-fueled student activism, that promoting open communication between students and educational managers can help in mitigating the

effects of social media activism, and that schools should collaborate with parents to monitor and guide students' social media use in relation to activism. However, from the responses of the respondents one can find that all above mentioned strategies can be implemented by educational managers to address challenges posed by social media-fueled activism as indicated by the average mean score of 2.69.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between male and female public senior secondary school students in the role that social media plays in their involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement

Table 4: t-test Analysis on the Mean Rating of male and female public senior secondary school students in the role that social media plays in their involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Standard Error	t _{tal}	t _{tab}	P-value	Remarks
Male	217	2.79	0.67	308	0.11	0.41	1.96	0.602	Accept Ho
Female	93	2.64	0.62						

The results in Table 4: revealed that the calculated t-value of 0.41 was less than the critical t-value of 1.96 when tested at 0.05 level of significance with 308 degree of freedom. This shows that the result is not significant. It implies that there is no significant difference between male and female public senior secondary school students in the role that social media plays in their involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained.

Discussion

The finding of this study revealed that the social media platforms are equally influential in encouraging both male and female students to participate in the movement. This aligns with contemporary research by Hoffman, (2020); Loader et al., (2014) on social media's role in political engagement. Studies show that social media creates an inclusive platform where both genders can equally access information, express opinions, and mobilize for collective action. Research question two reveals that the effects of students' involvement in the "End Bad Government" movement on the management of educational institutions have increased tension between students and educational administrators. This is supported by research by Boren (2001) showing that administrators, who uphold institutional policies and maintain order, and students, who desire change, frequently clash over activism. The movement has made adjustments to school policies and management practices in the area of policy and management. Morris's (2020) study demonstrates that persistent student activism frequently results in

institutional improvements, such as updated codes of conduct, improved student support services, and more communication between students and administrators. Data in table three revealed that item 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 had mean scores above the mean bench mark of 2.50; it implies that respondents agreed that educational managers should engage directly with students to address their concerns related to the "End Bad Government" movement. This finding is supported by empirical evidence indicating that direct engagement and dialogue between administrators and students can significantly reduce tensions and foster a more collaborative environment (Morris, 2020). By addressing concerns head-on, educational managers can build trust and potentially diffuse contentious situations before they escalate.

The t-test analysis of the mean evaluations of male and female students regarding the contribution of social media to their participation in the "End Bad Government" movement is shown in Table 4. At the 0.05 level of significance, the computed t-value of 0.41 is less than the crucial t-value of 1.96, suggesting that there is no statistically significant difference between the groups. According to this research, male and female students' use of social media to further the movement is not significantly different from one another. When it comes to their involvement, social media seems to have an equal impact on both genders. This finding aligns with previous research indicating social media acts as an equalizing medium for political participation, surpassing conventional gender norms (Hoffman, 2020; Gerbaudo, 2012).

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Because of this, the null hypothesis is upheld, confirming that there is no discernible difference in the impact of social media on activism between male and female students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the intersection of social media and the "End Bad Government" movement among public senior secondary school students in Mangu LGA, Plateau State, highlights the significant role digital platforms play in youth political activism. While empowering students to voice their concerns, it also presents challenges for educational management in maintaining academic focus and discipline. Effective management strategies that balance students' rights with educational responsibilities are essential to harness the positive aspects of this activism while mitigating its potential disruptions to the educational environment.

Recommendations

1. Educational managers should actively engage in open dialogue with both male and female students to address their concerns regarding the "End Bad Government" movement.
2. School administrators should develop and implement policies that acknowledge the role of social media in student activism.
3. It is recommended that educational managers receive training on the impact of social media on student behavior and activism. This training should equip them with the skills to manage activism-related challenges effectively and to create a supportive environment for student expression.

4. Schools should incorporate digital literacy programs into their curriculum to educate students on responsible social media use.

5. Educational institutions should collaborate with external stakeholders, including parents, community leaders, and policy makers, to create a unified approach to managing the effects of student activism.

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